

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B168
 Date: 3 Feb 2006
 Take Off 07:46:28 13:00:42
 Landing: 11:24:45 17:00:16
 Flight Time 3h38m17s 3h59m34s

Campaign: DABEX/DODO
Trials Instructions: Scientific Transit
Operating Area: Niamey to Bamako, Bamako to Dakar

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Aircraft Scientist	Jim Haywood	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	VACC	Jim McQuaid	University of Leeds
7	CCN / CVI / CCM2	Paul James	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
9	Filters	Paola Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
10	AMS 1	Paul Williams	University of Manchester
11	AMS 2	Gerard Capes	University of Manchester
12	Wet Neph	Simon Osborne	Met Office
13	Core Chemistry	Joss Kent	Met Office
14	Mission Scientist 1	Ellie Highwood	Reading University
15	Mission Scientist 2	Claire McConnell	Reading University
16	Mission Scientist 3	Hugh Coe	University of Manchester
17	Engineer	John Kitchen	Avalon Aero
18			

Flight Track:

B168 Track 03-FEB-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b168
 Date: 03 Feb 2006
 Project: DABEX to DODO Transit
 Location: Niamey to Bamako(Mali) to Dakar

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
063631		Startup		316	13'28.65N 2'10.53E
072855		INU		316	Set To Navigate
074628		T/O	1.5 kft	197	Niamey
074838		Videos	3.4 kft	348	Start FFC & DFC
074628	080429	Profile 1	4.1 - 18.0 kft	339	1000fpm
074924		ASPs	4.2 kft	336	Open
080429	081256	Profile 2	18.0 - 7.1 kft	320	1000fpm
081256	082735	Run 1	7.1 - 7.0 kft	318	
082735	083612	Profile 3	7.0 - 15.0 kft	319	
083647		Sonde	15.0 kft	319	Launch #01
083939	084603	Profile 4	15.0 - 8.0 kft	319	
084603	084729	Run 2	8.0 kft	322	
084730	085002	Profile 5	8.0 - 5.1 kft	322	
085002	085943	Run 3	5.1 - 4.5 kft	325	
085133		Event	5.0 kft	325	Change level
085224		Event	4.5 kft	326	Now Level
085944	090938	Profile 6	4.5 - 15.0 kft	324	
090939	091109	Run 4	15.0 kft	320	500fpm
091001		Sonde	15.0 kft	320	Launch 02
091109	091520	Profile 7.1	15.0 - 10.8 kft	320	500fpm, turning
091530	092442	Profile 7.1	10.6 - 5.0 kft	299	500fpm<FL90
092103		Videos	7.2 kft	230	Change tapes
092443	093529	Profile 7.2	5.0 - 10.0 kft	226	500fpm<FL90
			1000fpm - FL90		
093530	094553	Profile 7.3	10.0 - 5.0 kft	232	1000fpm - FL90
094553	100549	Profile 7.4	5.0 - 18.0 kft	226	150-158 @500fpm
100623		Sonde	18.0 kft	233	Launch #03
100549	100830	Run 5	18.0 kft	232	
100831	102535	Profile 8.1	18.0 - 1.3 kft	232	500'agl
102536	103828	Run 6	1.3 - 1.4 kft	228	500'agl Q1014
103255		Event	1.4 kft	267	Turning to fire
103526		Event	1.6 kft	248	Return to track
103828	105327	Profile 8.2	1.4 - 18.0 kft	214	Q1014, 1000fpm-FL70
105327	110032	Profile 8.3	18.0 - 11.0 kft	230	1000fpm-FL70
105859		Videos	12.5 kft	230	Change tapes
110032	110722	Run 7	11.0 kft	229	
110722	112035	Profile 9	11.0 - 3.3 kft	228	
112203		ASPs	3.4 kft	216	Close
112208	112445	Profile 9	3.3 - 1.2 kft	216	End
112445		Land	1.2 kft	056	Bamako
113027		Position		148	12'32.45N, 7'56.68W
124747		INU		148	To Navigate
130042		T/O	1.5 kft	057	Bamako
130042	130317	Profile 10	1.7 - 4.6 kft	073	
130231		ASPs	3.3 kft	213	Open
130326	131314	Profile 10	4.7 - 12.0 kft	280	
131333	131510	Run 8	12.0 kft	304	
131510	132241	Profile 10	12.0 - 18.0 kft	304	
132241	133159	Profile 11	18.0 - 10.0 kft	299	
133159	135116	Run 9	10.0 - 10.1 kft	297	
135117	135319	Profile 12	10.1 - 8.1 kft	298	
135320	141412	Run 10	8.1 - 8.0 kft	299	
135404		Videos	8.0 kft	298	Change tapes
141412	142534	Profile 13	8.0 - 18.0 kft	319	
142535	142835	Run 11	18.0 kft	310	
142610		Sonde	18.0 kft	310	Launch #04
142836	143824	Profile 14	18.0 - 10.1 kft	310	
143824	144101	Profile 15	10.1 - 11.5 kft	315	
144102	144410	Run 12	11.5 kft	302	

144410	144544	Profile 13	11.5 - 12.0 kft	302
144544	144744	Run 13	12.0 - 12.1 kft	301 Creep up
144756	144901	Run 13	12.2 - 12.4 kft	302 Climb to FL128
144907	145141	Run 13	12.4 - 12.8 kft	302 Lvl@145009
145141	145759	Profile 16.1	12.8 - 16.0 kft	300 500fpm
145800	151051	Profile 16.2	16.0 - 10.0 kft	298 500fpm, P16.1
151051	152214	Profile 16.3	10.0 - 15.5 kft	302
152350	153030	Profile 16.3	15.5 - 18.0 kft	210
152451		Videos	15.9 kft	207 Change Tapes
153031	153432	Run 14	18.0 kft	210
153128		Sonde	18.0 kft	210 Launch #05
153433	154825	Profile 17	18.0 - 3.5 kft	211 1000fpm
155729	160151	Profile 17	3.3 - 0.27 kft	202 ATC Inrupt min=170'
160151	161150	Run 15	0.27 - 0.32 kft	206
161435	162550	Run 16	1.5 - 1.6 kft	319 1500'
163047	163141	Orbit 1	1.0 - 1.1 kft	282 60 left, start @270
163224	163319	Orbit 2	1.1 kft	197 60 left, start @210
163544	163644	Orbit 3	4.2 - 4.1 kft	091 60 left, start @090
163715	163811	Orbit 4	4.1 kft	020 60 left, start @040
164123		ASPs	4.0 kft	158 Closed
170016		Land	0.20 kft	352 Dakar
171010		Shutdown	0.20 kft	358 14'44.45N,17'29.33W

B168 Track 03-FEB-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

DABEX/DODO transit (part a)

Flight No: B168a+b

Date: 3rd February 2006

Trial objectives:

To perform in-situ measurements of mineral dust on the transit from Niamey to Bamako and from Bamako to Dakar.

Location:

Areas to the north of the line Niamey – Dakar.

Weather:

High loadings of mineral dust preferred. Clear skies preferred.

Special requirements:

Low-level (500ft) flying over land.

Flight pattern (no cirrus present):

1. Take off from Niamey [08:00Z].
2. Perform profile ascent from Niamey airport to FL180.
3. Perform a series of profiles and SLRs at different altitudes on the way to Bamako along the predefined flight route.
4. Perform dropsonde lanches as deemed necessary by the aircraft scientist (3 suggested).
5. Profile descent to Bamako.
6. Land Bamako [T=230mins, Time=11:50Z]

Refuel Bamako

7. Take-off Bamako [13:00Z].
8. Perform profile ascent from Bamako airport to FL180.
9. Perform a series of profiles and SLRs at different altitudes on the way to Dakar along the predefined flight route.
10. Perform dropsonde lanches as deemed necessary by the aircraft scientist (3 suggested).
11. Profile descent to Dakar.
12. Land Dakar [T=230mins, Time=16:50Z]

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B168

Date: 3rd February 2006

Sortie Objectives: Transit flight from Niamey to Bamako

Operating area: Between Niamey and Bamako. Three dropsondes launched.

Weather: Variable amounts of cloud throughout the morning, which means that the radiation measurements will be difficult to disentangle.

Flight Patterns: Take off from Niamey was followed by a profile ascent from the ground to FL180. A thin layer of dust with peak scattering values of $300 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^{-1}$ was present at low level. Biomass burning aerosol was present between FL50 and FL120, but the scattering was not that large with a peak of around $50 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^{-1}$. SWS was set to nadir to look at the surface because the cloud amount was too large. A SLR at FL70 was performed for 15mins in the BB layer before a profile ascent was performed to FL150 to launch a dropsonde. The aerosol had thinned significantly upon return to FL80 so a slow (500ft/minute) sawtooth was performed 4500ft - FL150 - 5000ft. A second sonde was launched at FL150. A second sawtooth was performed from 5000ft - FL100 - 5000ft - FL180 - 500ft AGL. A third sonde was dropped at FL180. The environment was very clean. Little sign of the forecasted dust in the lee of the Hoggar mountains. At 500ft AGL a 12minute soft ride was performed including a brief off-track pass through a biomass burning fire. A profile was made then to FL180, a SLR was performed at FL110, before landing at Bamako.

Summary: Not much in the way of dust aerosol present and plenty of cirrus throughout the flight will make analysis of the radiation work difficult. SWS was nadir viewing throughout the flight, so could be used to provide e.g. NDVI.

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B168b

Date: 3rd February 2006

Sortie Objectives: Science transit Bamako to Dakar. First look at aerosol over the ocean.

Operating area: Land regions to the North of Bamako to Dakar line. Over ocean between Nautchokk and Dakar.

Weather: Clear skies. Some cirrus, and some mid-level cloud. Considerable haze at high level. Light winds. No dust.

Flight Patterns:

Take off from Bamako after refuelling. An interrupted profile ascent to FL180 was carried out to establish location of aerosol layer. The biomass layer of the morning flight was deep and had multiple structures between around 7000 ft and FL150. A straight and level run at FL100 was performed at the top of the biomass layer. Towards the north the signal became weaker at this level and we descended to FL080 to look for bottom of layer. This was followed by a profile ascent to FL180 when a sonde was dropped in the region of Gao. A profile descent to FL100 was made to allow more in-situ sampling of the aerosol layer. Cirrus was present in increasing amounts, with some mid cloud to the east. The aerosol layers became thinner and elevated further north, and a deep sawtooth profile was performed between FL100 and FL180. Sonde 2 was launched close to the Northern most point, after a turn to the south and just after passing the coast line. CuNb were visible to the east just shooting through the top of the biomass layer which was clearly visible. SWS was looking down at the surface during the passage over the coast line.

A deep profile descent over the ocean reached 170ft above the ocean. A 10 min low level run at 170ft was performed south towards Dakar. An aerosol layer was present below around 2000ft, with the remainder of some elevated biomass above. Several ship steaming through the area. Sea state calm, a few white ripples. A further 10 minute run was performed at 1500ft in the middle of the lowest layer. Some Ci towards Dakar, so turned west to perform one set of 2 orbits at 1000ft at 60 bank angle (SZA around 55). A further set of orbits were obtained at 4000ft at the top of the lowest aerosol layer. Subsequently we ascended to approach Dakar and to land. Clearly defined brown haze extending from Dakar peninsula west over ocean, thinning as moving away from coast..

Summary:

Good opportunistic radiative measurements and profiles of aerosol in marine environment. Some interesting surface characterisation over the coastal region. In situ biomass samples from early runs, and first marine samples from 1500ft run.

Problems

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.168**.....

Date **3rd Feb 2006**

Page **1** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Transit + science from Niamey → Bamako.
					Quite alot of Ci $\frac{7}{8}$ thin.
					QNH 1011mb.
					080° 8kts windspeed.
~ 07:47					T/O Niamey.
					Not too much haze.
					Clear slot 2,800ft - 5000ft
07:49:06	PI ↑				V. low CO at 80ppb in clear slot.
08:04:29	End P1 STP2	180 FL			
08:12:56	End P2 STR1	70 FL			In BB layer
					Lots of Ci + mid level cloud
					Not much dust below
					→ good vis, SWSN to look at surface.
08:19					Shadows visible on grounds
08:22					Crossing large rivers

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B**...168...

 Date ...3rd Feb 2006

Page ...2... of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Scat $\sim 50 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$.
08:27:35	End R1 St P3	FL70 ↑			Top of aerosol layer at FL90.
08:36:12	End P3	150 FL →			
					Unmarked run, 2nd launch #1.
08:39:39	St P4	150 FL ↓			Very clear below - not much aerosol around.
08:46:23	End AP4 St R2	80 FL →			BB has cleared.
08:47:30	End R2 St P5	80 FL ↓			
08:50:02	End P5 St R3	4500ft 5000ft			Very clean environment - no dust or BB - neph scat ~ 0
08:59:44	End R3 St P6	4500ft ↑			V. thin distinct BB layer between 6-9,000ft. Ci 4/8 above.
09:09:39	End R6 St R4	150 FL			Launch sende #2
09:11:09	St P7.1	150 FL ↓			
09:15					Gentle turn to the west.
09:24:43	End P7.2 St P7.2	5000ft ↑		17.7, 1.9	
09:35:29	End P7.3 St P7.3	100 FL ↓			Very clean environment still
09:45:53	End P7.4 St P7.4	5000ft ↑			Overhead Timbuktu
10:05:49	End P7.5 St R5	FL80 →			Launch dropsende #3.
10:08:31	End R5 St P8.1	180 FL ↓			Broad BB peak from FL150 → 8000ft.
10:25:36	End 8.1 St R6	5000ft			500ft softside.
					Village RHS at start of run.
					Through small BB fire

DA 16 mins from Kay.

Mission Scientist's Log

Kay - Grind 33 mins
 1/2 16 mins 1000ft/min

18000ft = 18 mins
 Need to start @ Kay.

Flight No **B.168b**

Date **3/2/06**

Page **1** of **.....**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
~125000					Transit and Science
					Bamako → Dakar
					~ 7/8 Ci + 5/8 low mid level cloud
					Some haze, mirage on runway!
13 01 09	T/O				7/8 Ci, scrubby vegetation below
		2300ft ↑			Air sample pipes open, heavy haze to
130326	P10 ↑	4600ft			Start profile from take off.
130826		4300ft 6400ft			clear slot ahead & right. Haze above & below
					flies to LHS
130326 128225	P10 Int				break in Cirrus ahead but cloudy elsewhere
	R8 start				
131510	R8 P10 res	FL120			
		FL150			Free troposphere, scattering background
					Cirrus above, Cu on RHS
130241	P10 cont P11 start	FL180 ↓			cloud towards top part of cloud ahead.
132922					~ 3/8 Ci above, top of haze layer
133159	P11 cont R9	FL100 →			Start run scat

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.168B**

Date

Page 2 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
133742	R9	FL100			64 sooty, sea 78 uncorr $w_0 \frac{80}{140} \frac{4}{7} \approx 0.65$
					Query PSAP filter wet in cloud? neph
134500	R9	FL100			
135119	R9 end P12 ↓	FL100 → FL080			Descending to find biomass. SWS ↑
135320	P12 end R10 start	FL080			Biomass curves
13 140630	R10 end R10	FL080			In and out of strong biomass. Ci gone overhead.
141412	R10 end P13 ↑	FL080 → FL180			top @ 14,400ft
142535	P13 end R11 start	FL180			Start run, small Cu below, cloud at our level ahead.
					Sonde launch (4)
142836	R11 end P14 ↓	FL180 FL100			Cumulus to North and RHS, less to LHS. Cirrus closer
					Aerosol Cloud Layers thinning & rising Sawtooth FL150 → FL100
					All well broke loose chasing layers → sorry!
145800	P16 ↓	FL100 FL100 ↓			CuNs on LHS ahead Ahead 7/8 1000-1500ft. Red ripples. Sloping up.
151051	P16.2 P16.3	FL100 FL180 ↓			Some scattered Cu
152214	P16.3 int	FL155			turning over Nantucket.
152350	P16.3 reconn.	FL155 ↑			Clouds at top of pollution layer on LHS
		FL173			contrail on LHS in distance

extend down or
run.

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.168B**

 Date 3/2/06

 Page 3 of 3

18 mins
10 mins
0 min
(38)
orbits
N
orbits

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
153033	P16.3 R 14	FL180			Out of aerosol layer, clouds at top
153128		FL180			top Sande
153433	P17↓	FL180 → 170ft			Cloud to left & right
155557	P17↓	4500ft			ship to left.
	P17end	170ft			scattered
160151	R15 start	170ft			seastate if some
					Scattered Cu so no orbits
161235	R16	1500ft			3/8 Cu above us.
162011	R16	1500ft			ship steaming L→R
162550	R16end	1500ft			Descend to 600ft, 1/8 Ci
163047	O1.1	1000ft 600ft	270		60° to left start
163141	O1.1				End orbit
163224	O2	1000ft	210		Some Ci
16	O2	1000ft			
		4000ft↑			
163544	O3	4000ft	090		above most aerosol in bottom layer.
163644	O3	end			end orbit
163745	O4	4000ft	040		Start orbit
163811	O4	4000ft			end of orbit
					More ships
					Approach to Dakar.
					Thin dust layer clearly coming from Dakar peninsula.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B168

Date: 3/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 05:40:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 7
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
07:49:06																Start Profile 1 from take-off	
07:49:28	20	0.10	Off	2	1											FL040	
07:51:17	155	0.10	Off	5	1											FL050	
07:52:24	440	0.11	Off	5	1											FL060	
07:53:33	400	0.11	Off	5	1											FL070	
07:54:45	300	0.11	0	5	1											FL080	
07:55:48	270	0.10		5	1											FL090	
07:56:46	300	0.10		10	1											FL100	
07:57:45	300	0.10		10	1											FL110	
07:58:40	55	0.11		5	1											FL120	
07:59:31	15	0.11														FL130	
08:00:29	10	0.10														FL140	
08:01:24	5	0.09														FL150	
08:02:26	7	0.09														FL160	
08:03:27	7	0.09														FL170	
08:04:30	7	0.09														End of Profile 1 & Start Profile 2 @ FL180	
08:05:16	8	0.07														FL170	
08:06:00	12	0.08														FL160	
08:06:50	13	0.07														FL150	
08:07:28	15	0.08														FL140	
08:08:20	30	0.10		3												FL130	
08:09:07	70	0.11		3	1											FL120	
08:09:42	270	0.11		5	1											FL110	
08:10:28	310	0.10		5	1											FL100	
08:11:19	400	0.11		5	1											FL090	
08:12:06	400	0.10		5	1											FL080	
08:12:57																End of Profile 2 & Start Run 1 @ FL070	
08:13:00	500	0.10		10	1												
08:15:00	500	0.11		10	1												
08:17:00	540	0.11	Off	10	1												
08:19:00	420	0.11	Off	10	1												
08:21:00	430	0.11	Off	10	1												
08:23:00	410	0.11	Off	10	1												
08:25:00	410	0.11	Off	10	1												
08:27:36																End of Run 1 & Start Profile 3 from FL070	
08:28:48	325	0.11	Off	10	1											FL080	
08:29:58	120	0.11	Off	5	1											FL090	
08:31:10	75	0.10	Off	5	1											FL100	
08:32:10	45	0.10	Off	5	1											FL110	
08:33:08	25	0.09	Off	5	1											FL120	
08:34:08	30	0.09	Off	2												FL130	
08:35:21	6	0.09	Off		Noise											FL140	
08:36:11	12	0.10	Off													End of Profile 3 @ FL150	
08:39:40	20	0.10	Off													Start Profile 4 from FL150	
08:40:30	18	0.09	Off	2												FL140	
08:41:23	30	0.09	Off	1												FL130	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B168

Date: 3/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 05:40:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 7
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
08:42:24	45	0.10	Off	2												FL120	
08:43:00	35	0.09	Off	1												FL110	
08:43:51	35	0.09	Off	1												FL100	
08:44:49	25	0.09	Off	1												FL090	
08:46:01																End of Profile 4 & Start Run 2 @ FL080	
08:47:00	20	0.09															
08:47:30																End of Run 2 & Start Profile 5 from FL080	
08:48:30	160	0.11	Off	1												FL070	
08:49:11	145	0.11	Off	1												FL060	
08:50:03																End of Profile 5 & Start Run 3 @ FL050	
08:51:00	20	0.10	Off	1													
08:53:00	20	0.10	Off														
08:55:00	10	0.10	Off		Noise												
08:57:00	15	0.10	Off	1	Noise												
08:59:00	20	0.10	Off	1	Noise												
08:59:43																End of Run 3 & Start Profile 6 from FL045	
09:01:23	30	0.08	Off		Noise											FL060	
09:02:23	125	0.10	Off	5	Noise											FL070	
09:03:15	60	0.09	Off	2	Noise											FL080	
09:04:17	18	0.09	Off	2												FL090	
09:05:12	30	0.09	Off	1	Noise											FL100	
09:06:09	40	0.10	Off	1												FL110	
09:07:01	35	0.10	Off	1	Noise											FL120	
09:07:56	20	0.10	Off	1	Noise											FL130	
09:08:45	20	0.10	Off	1	Noise											FL140	
09:09:35	18	0.10	Off	1	Noise											End of Profile 6 & Start Run 4 @ FL150	
09:10:00	10	0.10	Off	1	Noise												
09:11:09																End of Run 4 & Start Profile 7.1 from FL150	
09:12:13	30	0.11	Off	1	Noise											FL140	
09:13:12	40	0.11	Off	1	Noise											FL130	
09:14:12	25	0.11	Off	1	Noise											FL120	
09:15:17	50	0.11	Off	1	Noise											FL110	
09:16:03	66	0.11	Off	1	Noise											FL100	
09:17:05	45	0.11	Off	2	Noise											FL090	
09:19:18	20	0.09	Off		Noise											FL080	
09:21:11	50	0.10	Off	5	Noise											FL070	
09:22:54	25	0.11	Off	2	Noise											FL060	
09:24:43	10	0.08	Off		Noise											End of Profile 7.1 & Start Profile 7.2 @ FL050	
09:26:16	3	0.10	Off	1	Noise											FL060	
09:27:42	60	0.10	Off	3	Noise											FL070	
09:30:16	25	0.09	Off	1	1											FL080	
09:32:25	55	0.10	Off	2	Noise											FL090	
09:35:30	60	0.11	Off	2	Noise											End of Profile 7.2 & Start Profile 7.3 @ FL100	
09:37:40	50	0.10	Off	2	Noise											FL090	
09:39:34	80	0.10	Off	2	Noise											FL080	
09:41:50	15	0.09	Off	1	Noise											FL070	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B168

Date: 3/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 05:40:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 7
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:43:57	2	0.13	Off		Noise											FL060	
09:45:56	20	0.10	Off		Noise											FL050	
09:46:49	20	0.09	Off													FL060	
09:49:31	100	0.10	Off	5												FL070	
09:51:10	65	0.10	Off	5												FL080	
09:52:30	55	0.10	Off	5	Noise											FL100	
09:54:02	70	0.11	Off	3	Noise											FL110	
09:57:10	90	0.11	Off	4	Noise											FL120	
09:58:56	70	0.11	Off	3	Noise											FL130	
10:00:53	90	0.11	Off	3												FL140	
10:02:28	120	0.11	Off	3	Noise											FL150	
10:03:58	25	0.11	Off	2												FL160	
10:04:52	10	0.09	Off	1												FL170	
10:05:49	15	0.08	Off	1												End of Profile 7.3 & Start Run 5 @ FL180	
10:06:00	15	0.12	Off	1													
10:08:30																End of Run 5 & Start profile 8.1 from FL180	
10:09:35	25	0.12	Off	1	Noise											FL170	
10:10:28	15	0.12	Off	1												FL160	
10:11:33	18	0.12	Off	1												FL150	
10:12:18	130	0.11	Off	10	1											FL140	
10:13:14	270	0.11	Off	10	1											FL130	
10:14:11	140	0.11	Off	5	1											FL120	
10:15:05	100	0.11	Off	5	Noise											FL110	
10:15:54	110	0.11	Off	5	Noise											FL100	
10:16:57	110	0.10	Off	5	Noise											FL090	
10:18:01	110	0.10	Off	5	Noise											FL080	
10:19:07	90	0.10	Off	5												FL070	
10:20:07	15	0.08	Off	2												FL060	
10:21:04	40	0.09	Off	2												FL050	
10:22:10	15	0.09	Off		Noise											FL040	
10:23:04	60	0.10	Off	20	10											FL030	
10:25:36																End of Profile 8.1 * Start Run 6 @ 500'	
10:26:00	120	0.11	Off	30	10												
10:28:00	130	0.11	Off	30	10												
10:30:00	120	0.11	Off	30	10												
10:32:00	120	0.11	Off	30	6												
10:34:00	135	0.11	Off	30	7												
10:36:00	140	0.11	Off	40	10												
10:38:33																End of Run 6 & Start Profile 8.2	
10:39:10	110	0.12	Off	30	10											FL020	
10:39:54	65	0.10	Off	10												FL030	
10:40:43	17	0.08	Off													FL040	
10:43:20	100	0.10	Off	5	1											FL070	
10:44:15	90	0.10	Off	5	1											FL080	
10:45:16	110	0.10	Off	5	1											FL090	
10:45:48	250	0.10	Off	10	10											FL100	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B168

Date: 3/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 05:40:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 4 of 7
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:46:49	340	0.11	Off	15	10											FL110	
10:47:35	260	0.10	Off	10	1											FL120	
10:48:35	55	0.10	Off	3	1											FL130	
10:49:22	25	0.09	Off	2												FL140	
10:50:26	8	0.08	Off	2												FL150	
10:51:22	13	0.08	Off													FL160	
10:52:26	10	0.08	Off													FL170	
10:53:28	10	0.07	Off	2	1											End of Profile 8.2 & Start Profile 8.3 @ FL180	
10:54:30	10	0.09	Off		Noise											FL170	
10:55:32	15	0.09	Off													FL160	
10:56:37	15	0.08	Off	1												FL150	
10:57:35	150	0.10	Off	5	1											FL140	
10:58:30	125	0.11	Off	10	1											FL130	
10:59:30	440	0.11	Off	10	1											FL120	
11:00:37																End of Profile 8.3 & Run 7 @ FL110	
11:01:00	450	0.11	Off	10	1												
11:03:00	310	0.10	Off	10	1												
11:05:00	385	0.11	Off	10	1												
11:07:00	320	0.10	Off	10	1												
11:07:22																End of Run 7 & Start Profile 9 from FL110	
11:08:35	310	0.10	Off	10	1											FL100	
11:09:47	535	0.11	Off	10	1											FL090	
11:10:58	150	0.11	Off	5	1											FL080	
11:12:42	710	0.11	Off	10	10											FL070	
11:15:46	270	0.11	Off	5	10											FL060	
11:17:50	35	0.10	Off	5	Off											FL050	
11:18:55	100	0.12	Off	30	Off											FL040	
11:24:35																End of Profile 9	
13:03:20																Start Profile 10 from FL046	
13:04:02	100	0.10	Off	5	2											FL050	
13:05:13	90	0.10	Off	5	2											FL060	
13:06:31	360	0.10	Off	5	2											FL070	
13:07:39	410	0.10	Off	5	1											FL080	
13:08:53	400	0.11	Off	5	1											FL090	
13:10:11	310	0.11	Off	5	1											FL100	
13:11:42	290	0.11	Off	5	1											FL110	
13:13:14																Hold Profile 10 & Start Run 8 @ FL120	
13:14:00	300	0.11	Off	10	2												
13:15:39	250	0.11	Off	10	2											End of Run 8 & Continue Profile 10	
13:16:48	180	0.10	Off	5	2											FL130	
13:18:01	50	0.10	Off	2	1											FL140	
13:19:09	30	0.12	Off													FL150	
13:20:19	40	0.11	Off													FL160	
13:21:28	20	0.12	Off													FL170	
13:22:42	15	0.13	Off													End of Profile 10 & Start Profile 11 @ FL180	
13:24:16	35	0.13	Off													FL170	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B168

Date: 3/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 05:40:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 5 of 7
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
13:25:37	25	0.12	Off													FL160	
13:26:40	50	0.12	Off													FL150	
13:27:49	75	0.11	Off													FL140	
13:28:41	180	0.11	Off	5	1											FL130	
13:29:35	280	0.11	Off	5	1											FL120	
13:30:53	440	0.11	Off	10	1											FL110	
13:31:57																End of Profile 11 & Start Run 9 @ FL100	
13:32:00	500	0.11	Off	10	10												
13:34:00	640	0.11	Off	10	10												
13:36:00	880	0.10	Off	15	Noise												
13:38:00	700	0.10	Off	20	10												
13:40:00	1000	0.10	Off	20	15												
13:42:00	620	0.10	Off	30	Noise												
13:44:00	580	0.11	Off	20	10												
13:46:00	600	0.10	Off	10	10												
13:48:00	460	0.10	Off	10	10												
13:51:18																End of Run 9 & Start Profile 12 from FL100	
13:52:15	630	0.10	Off	10	Noise											FL090	
13:53:20																End of Profile 12 & Start Run 10 @ FL080	
13:54:00	1000	0.10	Off	10	Noise												
13:56:00	870	0.09	Off	10	Noise												
13:58:00	850	0.09	Off	10	Noise												
14:00:00	890	0.09	Off	10	Noise												
14:02:00	880	0.10	Off	10	10												
14:04:00	940	0.10	Off	10	10												
14:06:00	860	0.10	Off	10	Noise												
14:08:00	880	0.11	Off	10	Noise												
14:10:00	900	0.11	Off	10	10												
14:12:00	900	0.11	Off	10	Noise												
14:14:00	775	0.10	Off	10	Noise												
14:14:12																End of Run 10 & Start Profile 13 from FL080	
14:16:13	500	0.11	Off	10	Noise											FL090	
14:17:15	700	0.11	Off	10	10											FL100	
14:18:21	600	0.10	Off	10	Noise											FL110	
14:19:36	430	0.11	Off	10	Noise											FL120	
14:20:32	440	0.11	Off	10	Noise											FL130	
14:21:35	270	0.11	Off	5	Noise											FL140	
14:22:42	70	0.11	Off	3	Noise											FL150	
14:23:42	10	0.11	Off		Noise											FL160	
14:24:45	10	0.11	Off		Noise											FL170	
14:25:32																End of Profile 13 & Start Run 11 @ FL180	
14:26:00	7	0.13	Off		Noise												
14:28:00	5	0.09	Off		Noise												
14:28:36																End of Run 11 & Start Profile 14 from FL180	
14:30:06	15	0.11	Off		Noise											FL170	
14:31:16	40	0.09	Off		Noise											FL160	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B168

Date: 3/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 05:40:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 6 of 7
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
14:32:30	225	0.11	Off	5	Noise											FL150	
14:33:46	440	0.11	Off	10	Noise											FL140	
14:34:52	610	0.11	Off	10	10											FL130	
14:36:03	880	0.11	Off	10	Noise											FL120	
14:37:18	650	0.11	Off	10	Noise											FL110	
14:38:25	130	0.11	Off	5	Noise											End of Profile 14 & Start Profile 15 @ FL100	
14:41:02																End of Profile 15 & Start Run 12 FL115	
14:42:00	520	0.11	Off	5	Noise												
14:44:00	240	0.11	0	5	Noise												
14:44:10																End of Run 12 & Start Profile 16.1 from FL115	
14:45:44																End of Profile 16 & Start Run 13 @ FL120	
14:46:00	130	0.11		5	Noise												
14:48:00	135	0.11		5	Noise												
14:50:00	450	0.11		20												FL128	
14:51:41																End of Run 13 & Start Profile 16.1 from FL128	
14:53:54	300	0.11		5	Noise											FL140	
14:56:36	200	0.11		3	Noise											FL150	
14:58:00	130	0.11		5	Noise											End of Profile 16.1 & Start P 16.2 @ FL160	
15:00:10	185	0.11		5	Noise											FL150	
15:02:23	330	0.11		5	Noise											FL140	
15:04:55	570	0.11		15	3											FL130	
15:06:55	100	0.11		3	Noise											FL120	
15:08:51	145	0.11		3	Noise											FL110	
15:10:51	160	0.11		5	Noise											End of Profile 16.2 & Start P 16..3 @ FL100	
15:13:33	65	0.11		5	Noise											FL110	
15:15:34	100	0.10		5	Noise											FL120	
15:17:18	240	0.11		5	Noise											FL130	
15:19:50	190	0.11		5	Noise											FL140	
15:21:20	200	0.11		5	Noise											FL150	
15:25:09	165	0.11		5	Noise											FL160	
15:27:54	6	0.10		5	Noise											FL170	
15:30:33																End of Profile 16.3 & Start 14 @ FL180	
15:31:00	7	0.08			Noise												
15:33:00	5	0.10			Noise												
15:34:33																End of Run 14 & Start Profile 17	
15:35:43	100	0.11		2	Noise											FL170	
15:36:45	270	0.11		5	Noise											FL160	
15:37:20	300	0.11		5	Noise											FL150	
15:38:29	320	0.11		5	Noise											FL140	
15:39:20	800	0.11		10	Noise											FL130	
15:40:10	180	0.11		10	Noise											FL120	
15:41:06	110	0.10		5	Noise											FL110	
15:42:06	150	0.10		5	Noise											FL100	
15:43:05	190	0.11		5	Noise											FL090	
15:43:59	140	0.11		5	Noise											FL080	
15:44:56	35	0.09		3	Noise											FL070	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B168****Date:**

B) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	X X X	
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	X	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	X X X X X	
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	X X X X X N -	Note the calibration file used CAL27022006.TXT ZERO GLITCHES Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	X X	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto 20 seconds (!)
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	X X X X X	
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?	No water	
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		
iii) Alternative at 5b) is to use ,auto=602 or auto=605 to align FFSSP with Nevzorov LWC or TWC.		

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B168

Date:

C) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip		
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat iii) exit		Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N		Don't worry about lots of FORTRAN run-time errors as long as the program continues. These are format errors when writing to ascii files.
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)

Preparation of imagery for Core data product		
iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10	Creates files	PMSDATA: FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_Bnnn_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
iv) exit PVWAVE		
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO		
a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown i) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D		If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end. Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log. Note the particle type
10) In PVWAVE		
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' iii) exit		Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 9h) and 9j).
11) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?		

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B168

Date:

D) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
<p>1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:</p>		
<p>2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn</p> <p>b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT</p> <p>c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii)</p> <p>d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1 If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</p> <p>e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value. Calibration files to be stored in ????? Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³/sec</p> <p>f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d)</p> <p>g) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown</p> <p>h) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown</p>		<p>Note the min size channel Note the volume flow rate</p> <p>Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log.</p>
<p>3) In PVWAVE</p> <p>i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!</p> <p>ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat' 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp'</p> <p>iii) exit</p>		<p>Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 2g) and 2h).</p>
<p>4) MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp</p> <p>b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX</p> <p>c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name</p> <p>d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B168

Date:

E) NetCDF file preparation and ftp to BADC				
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments		
1) Run TAREXEC:MFD_BADC				
For inputs below, just press ENTER to use defaults				
a) MFD to convert: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX b) version number for BADC: r[0] c) Names file: TARDIS_ROOT:[CALTEXT.NETCDF]CP_NAMES.TXT d) Directory: [DATA_ROOT:[NETCDF]] e) File prefix: [core-cloud-phy_faam] f) File suffix: [] g) File for output: [core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.nc]		Defaults in [square brackets] As from 4c) above default NOT the default default default default Default name is generated		
2) Ftp transfer to BADC				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stage 1) creates two files: - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.nc - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.txt The *.txt file should be renamed to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn_descrip.txt but this cannot be done on VMS as the filename is too long You should do it if the file is first transferred to a PC, or after it has been uploaded to the appropriate "incoming" directory at BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd /incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core d) copy *.txt file as ascii e) copy *.nc and *2D-IMAGES.pdf files as binary				

F) BACKUP PROCEDURES		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Backup the intermediate files created in PMSDATA:		
a) zip "-V" PMSDATA:Bnnn*. * outdir:Bnnn_PMSDATA.zip Note that the uppercase "-V" option is important to preserve the VMS file characteristics when files are restored from this zip file.		Note destination directory "outdir"

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B168**Date:**

A) Raw data transfer to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer raw data files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt Bnnn_FFSSP.raw Bnnn_FFSSP_House_1.hse etc.		
2) Zip these file on the PC -output file: core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawffssp.zip		
3) Transfer SEADAS Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
4) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip) - rename Bnnn.zip to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawseadas.zip		
5) ftp to BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd incoming/faam/campaign_raw d) bin e) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawffssp.zip f) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawseadas.zip		Binary data transfer

Bags are numbers 1-140 and tubes are the other samples

Date	03/02/06	Tubes & Bags		Flight#	B168
T.O.	07:47:20	Land	11:24:40	NIM-BAM	Jim McQuaid (ULeeds)
T.O.	13:00:20	Land	17:01:01	BAM-DKR	
Tube/Bag #	START	END	Alt. (ft)	Sample Time	Comments
000097	08:16:00	08:18:00	7000	00:02:00	
000004	08:19:30	08:21:10	7000	00:01:40	
DO15379	08:21:30	08:25:20	7000	00:03:50	400 ml min-1
000034	08:25:25	08:27:40	7000	00:02:15	
CO8106	08:55:50	09:00:00	4500	00:04:10	400 ml min-1
DO15989	09:02:00	09:15:00	BLANK	00:13:00	BLANK
067698	09:09:50	09:14:30	15000	00:04:40	400 ml min-1
000036	10:24:50	10:25:50		00:01:00	
000066	10:26:00	10:26:50		00:00:50	"sixty six" written on bag
CO13546	10:27:00	10:32:30		00:05:30	
000123	10:32:50	10:34:00		00:01:10	
000137	10:34:05	10:35:00		00:00:55	
000021	10:35:10	10:37:15		00:02:05	
000019	13:34:15	13:37:20	10000	00:03:05	
DO21172	13:37:50	13:42:50	10000	00:05:00	400 ml min-1
000095	13:43:12	13:46:45	10000	00:03:33	
000078	13:47:00	13:48:30	10000	00:01:30	
067661	13:53:22	13:58:34	8000	00:05:12	400 ml min-1
062374	14:41:00	14:47:10	11500	00:06:10	400 ml min-1
000045	14:50:15	14:52:00	12800	00:01:45	trying the stay in the layer!
000018	14:52:45	14:54:30	12800	00:01:45	
000007	16:01:10	16:02:05	170	00:00:55	
000072	16:02:10	16:03:15	170	00:01:05	
000096	16:03:20	16:04:20	170	00:01:00	
062190	16:04:30	16:08:30	170	00:04:00	400 ml min-1
000031	16:08:50	16:09:50	170	00:01:00	
067603	16:15:30	16:21:00	1500	00:05:30	400 ml min-1

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B168

Date:

03 FEB 2006

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Whatman QMA (top)	Bottom inlet
Except for			

Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	B168Q1	----	----	Top	08:12:56	08:26:35	R1	1534	FL070
Filters run2_a	B168Q2	----	----	Top	08:50:02	08:59:44		961	FL050/FL045
Filters run 2_b	B168Q2	----	----	Top	09:35:00	09:58:00		2506	Sawtooth between 6000 and 9000 feet
Filters run 3_a	B168Q3	----	----	Bottom	10:24:00	10:34:00		1193	
Filters run 3_b	B168Q3	----	----	Top	10:36:00	10:38:28		259	
Filters run 4	B168Q4	----	----	Bottom	13:31:59	14:14:12	R9	3977	FL100
Filters run 5	B168Q5	----	----	Top	14:41:12	14:53:00		1029	FL115 up to FL128, possibly cloud contaminated
Filters run 6	B168Q6	----	----	Bottom	16:01:51	16:11:50		1372	170 feet over the sea
Filters run 7	B168Q7	----	----	Top	16:14:35	16:25:50		1395	1500 feet above sea possible ship contamination

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B...168**.....

 Date **..03/02/06..**

 Operator's name: **OSBORNE**.....

 Page **1** of **6**

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
	PCE-FLIGHT		CHECKS.					
			NEPH1 (DRY)	22.0				(good) zero signal small - \rightarrow small true. RH \sim 10% Flow rate \sim 20 lpm.
			NEPH2 (WET)	22.0				1 st attempt \rightarrow wandering signal (30s, 360s, 300s) 2 nd attempt \rightarrow much better. (60s, 360s, 400s)
080800								Start recording 6th neph to LABVIEW B, 8, water in chiller
0816								
0817						\downarrow	20°C	Chiller on, initially at \sim 20°C
0819	R1	FL370	11.7	15.5%	29.1%	\downarrow	10°C	Set to 10°C \sim 0.48 low!!
082320	R1	FL370	11.7	14.8%	27.1%	\rightarrow	25°C	SET TO RAMP UP.
082757	P27							CHILLER OFF FOR CLIMB UP
0842	P51							CHILLER ON During profile 080 \rightarrow 050
			12.7	0%	24.7%	\downarrow	15°C	SET
0855								CHILLER OFF AGAIN. almost zero aerosol.
0902					(SET)	\rightarrow	45°C	CHILLER ON.
			8.67	8.67	26%	\downarrow	42°C	RH \sim 98%, so set temp to 42°C
0909		FL150		5.7	66	\downarrow	40°C	SET =
091130						\rightarrow	42°C	SET
091620			12.0	14.5	72	\rightarrow	45°C	SET T ₁ = 27.7°C

Wet Nephelometer Log

Flight No **B...168**.....

Date **03/02/06**.....

Operator's name: **O. S. BRENF**.....

Page **2** of **4**.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
		FL080↓		0%	75%	↔	45°C	MAX T _{water} . RH = 84% But v. little aerosol amount. RH S values differs up & down, but wet neph RH pretty constant.
100130		R2146↑	9.8	5.2%	85.0%	↔	45°C	85% not too bad. RH S = 87.2%
1003								Wet neph reading -ve when dry neph is $5 \times 10^{-6} m^{-1}$
1020	↓	R2064	10.3	1.1	85.6%	↔	45°C	wet neph still -ve → went +ve at some points, can get v. high RH by lowering flow to ~5 l/min.
								Can get v. high RH by lowering flow to ~5 l/min.
								↳ in CBL C ₀₀₃ 6.5 σ = 24 IT
102536	R6	500↑	11.2	10.6	82.5	-	45°C	$\bar{w}_g \sim 0.6$ at 0.55 μm
104700	↗	R2128↑	10.3	13.2	90.1			Wet aerosol plume - biomass? \bar{w}_g up to units!! ↳ quite shallow, though.
1106	→	FL110	10.7	17.1	89.5	↔	45°C	good run in biomass (?) $w_{uncorr} \sim 0.75$!!
1108	↓	= probe.						See Dropping Tent.
130042								T ₀ Biomako.
132300	↖	FL180	10.3	3.1%	77%	↔	45°C	chiller on & set to 45°C T ₀ = 31.1°C.
133240	→	R2100	10.8	13.8	74%	↘	15°C	set to ramp down. (T _{combust} = 29.6°C)
134510	→	R2100	10.7	17.1	29.5	↗	30°C	SET
134810	→	R2100	10.7	20	45	↗	35°C	SET
134946	→	R400	10.6	19.4	51	↗	40°C	SET

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B**.....¹⁶⁹.....

 Date ...^{03/02/06}.....

 Operator's name: ...^{OS BURNETT}.....

 Page ...³ of ...⁴

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
135112	R12b	R2100	11.2	17.1	63.2	↓	45°C	Set (start of descent FL000 → FL080)
135408	R10	R2080	10.7 10.9	14.8	72.1	↔	45°C	RH5 = 90.4%
135650	R10	R2080	10.8	15.8	70.2	↓	15°C	Set RAMP Down ALL THE WAY
140320	R10	R2080	10.9	16.1	37.2	↑	45°C	RAMP UP Go!
141030								dry neph signal: 75 x 10 ⁻⁶ m ³ air
	↪ R10	R2080	10.7	17	74	↓	15°C	SET
						↗	35°C	RAMP UP.
14220	↗	R2150 R22	10.2	9.3	51	↗	45°C	Set
147260								out of aerosol now.
147320		R2151						Enter to p of aerosol.
1448			12.2	14.5	79.0	↔	45°C	In v. humid layer cloud above us RH ~ 95% !!
145040						↘	15°C	Set & cancelled.
145100			12.2 12.3	12.2	80.8	↗	45°C	Set to max for saw tooth. thin aerosol layer
1546	↓	R2050	12.1	1.8	83.7	↔	45°C	reasonable humidity
1559	↓	R2020	12.6	6	80	—	45°C	In MB? DUST? (red) → (green) → (blue) !! W ~ 0.70
1606		1700ft	12.1	10	70	↓	15°C	↓ SET TO RAMP Down.
161230		1700ft	11.9	8.3	37	↗	45°C	Set to max T _{water} at end of low-level run
161730		1500ft	11.3	4.4	72	↓	15°C	
162230		1500ft	11.5	5.7	39	↗	45°C	RAMP UP.

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 168

Date: 3rd February 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	N		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	Y
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	Y
		AMS	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	N	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	Y
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	Y
WAS	Y	Tube Sampling	Y

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B168

Date: 03 February 2006

Instruments

1. Upper and Lower Pyrometers – signal noisy
2. JW not operated
3. FFC & UFC Windows need to be cleaned
4. HORACE Displays – some pc displays locked up. Flight Manager's okay. Restart displays then okay.

Not fitted: ARIES, MARSS, DEIMOS

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom Calls

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B168:

Log	Reason
CCN	The instrument appears not to have been operated as there is no log sheet
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
VACC	No log is taken/provided for VACC

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

5 x Forward Facing Cameras
5 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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